

ESWC 2025 – Proceedings of the Project Networking Track

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Abstract

The Project Networking track at ESWC 2025 provided a platform for research projects to share their objectives, outcomes, and future directions with the Semantic Web community. This document outlines the track’s purpose and scope, summarizes the participating projects – funded by both national and European programs – and highlights the thematic diversity of their contributions. Each project is included in the track proceedings with a concise overview of its relevance, results, and collaborative potential.

Keywords

project networking, semantic web, knowledge graphs, ESWC 2025

1. Introduction

The Project Networking track has become a recurring and valued feature of the European Semantic Web Conference (ESWC), offering a space for research projects to connect, exchange, and grow. At the 2025 edition, the track once again brought together initiatives working, among other topics, on knowledge graphs, ontologies, data spaces, and the application of large multimodal models (LMMs) to knowledge engineering – core themes of the Semantic Web community.

This track continues to serve as a catalyst for collaboration, enabling projects at different stages – concluding, ongoing, or upcoming – to share insights, align goals, and explore synergies. Whether through the dissemination of results, the discussion of technical challenges, or the identification of future funding opportunities, the Project Networking track fosters a vibrant ecosystem of cooperation.

The selected contributions reflect the diversity and ambition of the respective projects, and we hope they inspire new connections and continued dialogue beyond the conference.

2. Selected Projects

The 2025 edition of the Project Networking track included two rounds of submissions (cf. call for contributions at <https://2025.eswc-conferences.org/call-for-project-networking/>) and brought together a diverse set of research initiatives. In total, 13 projects were submitted and accepted, reflecting a broad interest in exchanging experiences and exploring potential synergies within the ESWC community.

Of these, ten projects were funded by the European Union – DATABRI-X [1], DSSC [2], ENEXA [3], GLACIATION [4], HARNESS [5], INTEND [6], KATY [7], Onto-DESIDE [8], REEVALUATE [9], and SmartEdge [10]. Three additional projects – ConCur [11] (UK), PASSAT [12] (Austria & Germany), and SOEL [13] (Spain) – were supported by national funding schemes. A tag cloud summarizing the main topics addressed by these projects is presented in the following Figure 1.

Each of the accepted projects is briefly presented in these proceedings. These descriptions include key information such as project objectives, funding details, consortium partners, and relevance to the ESWC community. They also highlight the value each project brings to the Semantic Web field – through datasets, ontologies, tools, or methodologies – as well as what they hope to gain from engaging with

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